

Unilateral absence of musculocutaneous nerve

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ABSTRACT Detailed knowledge of the course and distribution of the nerves of the brachial plexus is critical in the management of nerve injuries, particularly in the case of anatomical variations. During routine dissection for undergraduate students, unilateral absence of the musculocutaneous nerve was observed in the right arm of an adult male cadaver. Direct branches of the median nerve innervated all the anterior compartment muscles of the arm.

KEYWORDS Musculocutaneous Nerve, Brachial Plexus, Arm

Introduction

The primary muscle compartments in the arm, forearm and intrinsic muscles of the hand are each innervated predominantly by branches from the brachial plexus (Moore et al., 2015). The brachial plexus itself is formed by the union of the ventral rami of the lower four cervical spinal nerves and the more significant part of the first thoracic ventral ramus (Standring et al., 2008; Moore et al., 2014), which constitute the roots of the plexus (Moore et al., 2015).

The roots of the brachial plexus unite to form three trunks; superior, middle and inferior trunks.

Each of these trunks divides into an anterior and a posterior division (Saladin 2008; Moore et al., 2014; Drake et al., 2015). Standring et al., (2008) and Moore et al. (2014) described that the anterior divisions of the superior and middle trunks unite to form the lateral cord, anterior division of the inferior trunk continues as the medial cord, while the posterior divisions of all three trunks unite to form the posterior cord.

Median nerve is formed by the union of the terminal branches of the medial and lateral cords, and supplies all the anterior compartment muscles of the forearm (Gumusburun et al., 2000; Drake et al., 2015) except flexor carpi ulnaris and medial half of flexor digitorum profundus (Moore et al., 2015; Standring et al., 2008) which are supplied by the ulnar nerve.

The musculocutaneous nerve is a continuation of the lateral cord (Drake et al., 2015). It supplies the coracobrachialis, biceps brachii and brachialis muscles (anterior or flexor compartment muscles of the arm) (Ihunwo et al., 1997; Gumusburun et al., 2000) and then terminates by continuing into the forearm as the lateral cutaneous nerve of forearm, thus, also providing innervation to the skin on the anterolateral side of the forearm (Standring et al., 2008; Moore et al., 2014).

Case report

During routine dissection for undergraduate students, using standard dissection techniques, unilateral absence of the musculocutaneous nerve was observed in the right arm of a male adult cadaver. The median nerve was formed by the lateral cord and the lateral root of the medial cord; the musculocutaneous nerve, which is usually a continuation of the lateral cord of the brachial plexus was absent. The median nerve took over the supply of the muscles in the anterior compartment muscles of the arm.

The lateral and medial roots of the median nerve (7) emerge from the axilla in close relationship with the axillary artery (5) and vein (6). In the arm, the median nerve first gave off a branch to coracobrachialis (a) and then continues distally to give off branches to biceps (b), brachialis (c) and a branch that continued laterally into the forearm as the lateral cutaneous nerve of forearm (d). Both medial and lateral roots of the median nerve were of the same size.

The musculocutaneous nerve, which is usually a continuation of the lateral cord, passes laterally, penetrates the coracobrachialis innervating it and then passes between the biceps brachii and brachialis, sending branches to both muscles (Drake et al., 2015; Standring et al., 2008; Moore et al., 2014) was completely absent.

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Fig. 1 Distribution of branches from the median nerve with the absence of the musculocutaneous nerve. 1. Pectoralis major 2. Biceps brachii 3. Coracobrachialis 4. Brachialis 5. Axillary artery 6. Axillary vein 7. Branches from the median nerve (a – Branch to coracobrachialis, b – branch to biceps, c – branch to brachialis and d – the lateral cutaneous nerve of the forearm) 8. Ulnar nerve

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Conclusion

The observed variation implies that an injury to the median nerve in the axilla would result in more extensive clinical symptoms. In addition to the paralysis of the muscles normally supplied by the median nerve in the forearm and hand, the muscles in the anterior compartment of the arm would also be paralysed. This will be presented as paralysis of the flexor muscles of the elbow and hypohypthesis of the lateral surface of the forearm.

Competing Interests

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